

The COVID-19 pandemic in the Cyclades: patterns and prospects in cultural tourism

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Abstract

Until July 2021, the repercussions of the Covid-19 pandemic were severe for tourism-dependent countries, such as Greece, and particularly the Cyclades. The cultural sector and related activities, at the crux of Cycladic tourism industry, were especially hit by the pandemic. The rest of the 2021 tourist season, however, proved especially successful for Cycladic tourism, which poses the question of why and how a destination may survive—and even profit—from the pandemic. This paper thus explores emerging Cyclades tourism patterns and prospects (in a case study of Andros, Syros, and Santorini), in the context of the anticipated post-pandemic tourism regeneration. Methodologically, the study was based on a) a series of in-situ in-depth interviews with key informants, a b) questionnaire survey of tourists and related local businesses, and c) a focus group panel discussion with key local/ regional stakeholders. The study was conducted between the fall of 2020 and spring of 2021, in the context of the SPOT HORIZON2020 EU project; the research design and data interpretation were enriched by participant observation and consultation of Trip Advisor websites. Findings show that the pandemic and its repercussions were grave for these islands, highly dependent on tourism based on a dominant small-and-medium-enterprise tourism development model. Modes of travel, types of tourism, and visitors' behaviour were altogether affected, resulting in new patterns of (im)mobilities, while the role of culture was viewed as the destination's 'hope in the horizon' towards the reigniting and regeneration of smaller-scale, creative, dispersed, and more sustainable tourism. However, great disparities also emerged between the current state and regenerative potential for local cultural tourism development. The study participants specifically emphasized that the private tourism sector had been left by the State to their own devices, and pointed to a lack of a) cultural infrastructure, b) public funding, and c) destination marketing/ promotion.

Keywords: tourism-dependent destinations, tourism trends, Covid-19 pandemic, cultural tourism, Cyclades

Introduction

In the context of severe instability and uncertainty that the Covid-19 (SARS-CoV-2) pandemic caused during the past couple of years, tourism has undergone a variable change and regrouping. This paper explores cultural tourism patterns and prospects emerging from the pandemic, in the context of the anticipated post-pandemic tourism regeneration, using the case study of the Cyclades, Greece and specifically the islands of Andros, Syros, and Santorini. It aims to probe and understand trends and characteristics of such (im)mobilities, and specifically culture-related tourist attractions and movements, from both tourists and destination actors. The approach is a case-study analysis, intending to contribute to theory and empirical knowledge on current change in the tourism sector, and specifically in heavily tourism-dependent economies/ societies, such as the Greek islands.

A turn towards more 'green' and sustainable tourism, favouring outdoor locations and less crowded, safe, and protected destinations emerged with the pandemic (INSETE, 2021; Knezevic et al., 2021; Purcell et al., 2020). Hence, the significance and centrality of the natural environment ('nature') to contemporary tourism cannot be contested. The lure of culture in contemporary tourism trends, however, is less obvious and more tentative, rendering research into culture-motivated tourism ('cultural tourism') very useful and timely (Jacobsen et al., 2021; UNWTO, 2021). The complex, reciprocal, and manifold role of culture in shaping a more sustainable future in tourism is very promising: cultural tourism can be 'green' enough, versatile enough, attractive enough, socially equitable enough, and economically lucrative enough, in times of change.

Based on the considerations laid above, this exploratory study turns to those who propel and enact tourism trends, that is the tourists themselves, but also significant local tourism actors and stakeholders, in an effort to understand the mechanisms of such trends, at the destination scale, at a world-famous destination, such as the Cyclades, Greece. Specifically, this study aims

to identify immediate problems and new trends concerning Cyclades' cultural tourist activities, businesses, and institutions affected by this crisis. It intends to capture the opinions, visions, and recommendations of those involved in local/ regional cultural tourism, as regards the latter's future reinstatement and growth. Such an exploration of the changing context of cultural tourism inevitably exposes long-underlying structural problems of Cyclades tourism and addresses the pandemic's effect on mind sets and aspirations, opening up opportunities and new horizons, towards more sustainable future tourism planning, promotion, and management.

At this significant crossroads of crisis and change, this research aims to contribute to contemporary tourism studies by providing a comprehensive, destination-based insight into the ongoing dynamic transformation and future prospects of the tourism sector at small tourism-dependent destinations. The role of culture—the competitive edge of Greek island tourism vis-à-vis other similar global destinations—is largely unexplored in regards to its potential contribution to future sustainable tourism, emerging from transformative processes stemming from current crises, natural or otherwise.

1. Theoretical background

Mobility, including tourism, is an ever-changing area of knowledge, co-constituted by perspectives and practices involving geographers and other social scientists, alongside other stakeholders and agents at various geographical scales (Cresswell, 2014; Cresswell & Merriman, 2011; Kwan & Schwanen, 2016). Over the past few decades, there has been increasing research interest in the social sciences in studies of tourism, transportation, and mobility, through increasingly nuanced, critical, hermeneutic, ethical, more-than-representational perspectives (Cidell et al., 2021; Kwan & Schwanen, 2016; Lorimer, 2007; Prince, 2018; Prince & Ioannides, 2017; Sheller & Urry, 2006). Often, attributed to the new mobilities paradigm (Sheller & Urry, 2006), the moral and/or critical encounters in tourism

(Bianchi, 2009; Caton, 2012; Scheyvens, 2012), the performance turn in tourism geography (Edensor, 2001), and various other advances in this scientific field, the study of mobility has acquired key ontological status in geography and other social sciences (Kwan & Schwanen, 2016). Concomitantly, tourism studies have tended to engage with or take into account all aspects of human life contributing to or affected by factors that produce tourism spaces/ places/ landscapes, movement, sustainability, development, and identity. These research inroads are currently compounded by the Covid-19 pandemic (Jacobsen et al., 2021; Knezevic et al., 2021), but also represent a basis for furthering and developing pertinent knowledge in times of great fluidity and future uncertainty.

The pandemic arrived at a time when global tourism was beginning to become unsteady against the background of global economic slowdown, Brexit, geopolitical and other tensions (DeMicco et al., 2021; UNWTO, 2020). However, despite some major shifts in the tourism sector, up until 2020, tourism arrivals and expenditure had continued to grow (UNWTO, 2020), a trend that also reflects tourism trends at the top Greek destinations (INSETE, 2020; INSETE, 2021). In 2020, the country welcomed about 7.4 million international travellers, whereas the number of inbound visitors in Greece had peaked at roughly 34 million in 2019 (INSETE, 2021). In fact, in 2019, Greece found itself in the 8th global position, as regards export revenues from tourism, among countries with the largest surplus in the travel balance (UNWTO, 2020, p. 5) and in the 7th position, with other countries, as regards the contribution of tourism to its economy (direct tourism GDP as a % of total GDP) (UNWTO, 2020, p. 6).

Among the most world-renowned tourism destinations in Greece, and highly competitive vis-à-vis other top global destinations (Berg & Edelheim, 2012; INSETE, 2020), the Cycladic islands have always been extremely dependent on tourism for their economic survival (INSETE, 2020). The Southern Aegean islands (Cyclades and Dodecanese) tend to attract 1 out of 4 tourists visiting Greece (INSETE, 2020; Statista 2021). The significance, but

also the conflicts, of tourism development, as well as the structural inefficiencies it exposes in SIDS (Small Island Developing States) and other small economies have been established (Britton, 1982; Oppermann, 1993; Williams & Montanari, 1999; Scheyvens, 2012; Scheyvens & Momsen, 2008). However, the Cyclades belong to a different category of islands of a more economically developed, but still highly tourism-dependent, country (Constantoglou & Klothaki, 2021; Medová et al, 2021; TheGlobalEconomy.com, 2022; WTTC, 2021). Not much comprehensive research has yet been carried out on such destinations (i.e., small Mediterranean islands), in the course of the pandemic with an outlook towards its aftermath (Ferretti, 2021). Furthermore, as we will show below, the Cyclades' cultural heritage and assets tend to be their most significant comparative advantages distinguishing and upholding them as tourism destinations, vis-à-vis their competitors. The broad spectrum of these cultural assets elicits variable cultural tourism, a form of tourism that has been significantly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic and its global and local repercussions (Jaquinto, 2022; Jacobsen et al., 2021; Knezevic et al., 2021).

Defined as 'a whole way of life' (Throsby, 2008), culture represents the highest-level, most deeply ingrained, holistic, integrative, and stable system of reference in human life. As such, it engulfs all tangible and intangible manifestations of human life and generates human mobilities attributed to 'culture' or 'cultural tourism'. The latter refers to the compound set of activities of tourism planning, effectuating, and experiencing a destination, with the—broadly defined—motive of culture (Mandic & Kennell, 2021; Richards, 2018). For the purposes of our study, we adopted the UNWTO definition of cultural tourism as 'a type of tourism activity in which the visitor's essential motivation is to learn, discover, experience and consume the tangible and intangible cultural attractions/products in a tourism destination' (Tsartas et al., 2020, p.18). We will proceed to explore the characteristics, changes, and prospects of such tourism, through

tourist 'eyes', in three Cycladic destinations, in order to gain an understanding of these extremely tentative, fluid, and ambivalent tourism (im)mobilities.

2. Research design

2.1 Description of the case study area

The selection of our case study rests on a series of considerations. The Cycladic Archipelago of Greece was selected, a) as a significant global tourism destination, b) as a case of a small-island tourism-dependent destination, but also c) based on its especially rich past and present cultural heritage, constituting its distinctive tourism-attraction profile and competitive edge. The Cyclades (Figure 1), and especially the islands of Mykonos and Santorini, are among the most world-renowned and highly-competitive global-tourism destinations in Greece (Berg & Edelheim, 2012; Coccossis, 2001; INSETE, 2020; WTTC, 2020), with significant implications for these islands' economic survival and development. Indicatively, international tourist air arrivals in the Cycladic islands in 2019 reached 994,000 according to official statistical data (INSETE, 2020). Cultural tourism differs from island to island (Terkenli & Georgoula, 2021), and it does not represent a conscious tourism motive for most Cyclades visitors; however, broadly defined, culture remains the factor that underlies tourists' decision to visit these islands. As attested by Trip Advisor travellers' choices and reviews (2022), besides the islands' strong 3Ss (sea-sand-sun) allure, the Cyclades also boasts striking natural/environmental assets, great landscape diversity, and rich cultural traditions and heritage (Berg & Edelheim, 2012; Prokopiou et al., 2018). On the negative side, their incoming tourism may not only enjoy the assets but also suffer the limitations, of their fragile insular character (e.g., smaller-scale destinations, insularity-induced resource limitations). On the positive side, however, local Cycladic communities tend to be much more closely knit and tightly linked with their cultural traditions than other parts of Greece or other island groups (Stewart, 2016, p. 29). Thus, it is their cultural attractions that render them a most significant pole of both local and international

tourism attraction, constituting a competitive advantage vis-à-vis other similar global destinations.

Generally speaking, the Cycladic islands feature small- and medium-scale tourism, as opposed to an ‘industrial’ model of tourism, since they are not as heavily reliant on mass/ package visitor inflows (with the exception of Mykonos and Santorini), a trend also reflected in the locally supplied types of accommodation (Oikonomou, 2000; Sarantakou, 2017; Sarantakou & Tsartas, 2015). The latter include family operations, to a very high degree- some of which may also not be formal/ institutionalized. Nonetheless, when destinations, such as Santorini, gain more international popularity and tourism investments, they tend to attract more privately-owned businesses or become part of international hotel chains. The growth and development of all other sectors of the local/ regional economy in the Cyclades (such as primary-sector activities, services, culture, and gastronomy) tend to follow those of tourism, which constitutes the main source of income for the whole region (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011; Tsartas et al. 2020).

The research survey was undertaken on three Cycladic islands (Andros, Santorini, and Syros), featuring a certain diversity in the character of their incoming tourism, so as to capture the variability and differentiation in Cyclades cultural tourism (Trip Advisor, 2022) without, however, losing their Cycladic tourism identity (the three islands’ similarities supersede their differences). Syros Island (population: 21.507, Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011) was selected for our study purposes as the main administrative centre of the Cycladic Archipelago and an island with a fairly vibrant economy that does not rely solely on tourism, as well as for its cultural tourism attractions (e.g., festivals and architecture). Santorini (population: 15.550, Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011) was selected based on its worldwide reputation as a top tourist destination and its spectacular cultural landscape. Finally, Andros (population: 9.221,

Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2011) was selected as a mainly domestic tourism and second-home destination, as well as for its alternative (ecotourism and art tourism) attractions.

Figure 1. The case study of Cyclades: Andros, Santorini, and Syros Islands.

3.2 Methodology

The study relied on a multi-methodological approach, undertaken and effectuated in the context of the SPOT HORIZON2020 EU project, which focuses more generally on cultural tourism and Europeanization, aiming towards sustainable development benefitting host communities and regional economies [SPOT Proposal Part A, p.3, <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu>]. The objective of this exploratory study was to describe comprehensively emerging patterns and prospects of cultural tourism trends, as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic from the perspective of the tourists, related businesses, and local stakeholders, using the case study of the Cyclades, Greece. For this purpose, the study employed an on-site intensive questionnaire survey (including both open-ended and closed-ended questions), eliciting both quantitative and qualitative data, and addressed separately to tourists and businesses. The findings were contextualized and supplemented by insights drawn from other related sources of relevant information. Specifically, for purposes of triangulation, the methodology comprised of a) a tourist and local businesses' on-site survey (two different questionnaires), b) in-depth stakeholder interviews, and c) a round-table discussion among agents of cultural tourism in the Cyclades. The research design and data interpretation were enriched by participant observation and consultation of Trip Advisor websites. We developed our three research questions on the basis of relevant bibliography and on-site participant observation, as follows:

Research question 1: What is the impact of the pandemic and consequent governmental measures on Cycladic tourism patterns during the pandemic (end of tourism season summer—fall 2020)?

Research question 2. What is the impact of the pandemic and consequent governmental measures on Cyclades tourism businesses, at the same time period?

Research question 3: What is the outcome/ reactions to the pandemic and consequent governmental measures for Cyclades cultural tourism (for the tourists and the local side) as a result (before—after the pandemic), at the same time period?

All three methodological approaches were employed for data collection, in order to respond to all three research questions. The questionnaire survey was conducted by the authors through on-site visits to the three islands of the case study, between 25/7/2020 and 25/9/2020. On each island, fieldwork took place in three locations, selected on the basis of statistical and Trip Advisor data (in terms of number and content of entries referring to the 3 islands) as characteristic of the range of different aspects and features of tourism and culture, in order to ensure a certain degree of representativeness vis-à-vis these two aspects. Specifically, we surveyed both urban and rural/ small town locations of both high and low tourist concentration/ development. On the island of Andros, responses from 40 tourists and 17 local business representatives were collected in a) the heavily touristic town of Batsi, b) the capital of the island Chora, and c) the less touristic fishing village of Korthi. In Syros, responses from 13 tourists and 9 local businesses were obtained in a) the highly touristic seaside resort of Galissas, b) the capital city of Hermoupolis, and c) smaller inland towns/villages. Finally, in Santorini (Thira), responses from 18 tourists and 30 business representatives were collected from a) the heavily touristic town of Oia, b) the capital of the island Fira (Thera), and c) the less touristic and more residential town of Emporio.

Structured questionnaires to both tourists (71 in total) and local businesses (56 in total) were administered in written and/or electronic form, using Google forms, whereas some respondents preferred on-the-spot completion in the form of an interview. Our tourist

respondents were approached in person in central squares, local shops, hotel lobbies and grounds, cafes, bus/port stations, and seaside promenades. The small size of our survey samples reflects the difficult circumstances we encountered in securing respondents who would be willing to take the time to engage with us, and the low overall numbers of visitors to the Cyclades, at that time. Finally, the quantitative (closed-ended questions) findings were organized, analysed, and manipulated with the aid of descriptive statistics (Microsoft Excel Version 16.0). However, as this was a small non-representative survey, it is possible to present only general descriptive statistics. The qualitative findings were organized and brought into the data analysis and interpretation as insights complementing and elucidating the quantitative findings.

The in-depth stakeholders' interviews (semi-structured questionnaires) were undertaken by the authors/ researchers at the outset of the questionnaire survey, in September 2020, with the purpose of collecting all pertinent information on cultural tourism in the Cyclades, but, more importantly, in order to elicit opinions, perceptions, and visions concerning cultural tourism in the Cyclades from major relevant local actors and stakeholders. Specifically, interviews were conducted with senior executives from the Departments of Culture of the Municipalities (local authorities) of Andros, Thira (Santorini), and Syros. The interviews were transcribed and data organized; insights pertaining to the objective of this paper will be presented and discussed in the Discussion section, below, together with the survey results and the round-table findings. The results of the stakeholders' round-table (focus-group) discussion (July 2021) were similarly organized and analyzed by the researchers, in order to capture changes in cultural tourism patterns, trends, and pandemic repercussions our case study, at a later and more recent stage of the Covid-19 pandemic impact on tourism. The round-table comprised of the researchers and the study's available stakeholders at the time, namely the Cyclades Ephor of Antiquities, the Head of the Department of Development and Documentation of the Cyclades

Chamber of Commerce, and the Senior Executive of the Audio Visual, Media, and Production Department—Division of Tourism Promotion—of the National Tourism Organization of Greece. After briefly addressing the status quo and policy framework of cultural tourism in the Cyclades, as well as its role in the local societies, the participants were asked to express a) their perceptions and assessment of the new parameters introduced to cultural tourism in the Cyclades by the pandemic and concomitant government measures, and b) their assessment/evaluation of future visions on local/ regional cultural tourism development.

3. Survey Results

After a brief presentation of our tourists' sample (Table 1) and businesses' sample (Table 2), this section lays out the tourists and businesses questionnaire survey outputs, ordered by research question. The first research question comprises two questionnaire questions, the second one comprises five, and the third one comprises one questionnaire question.

Table 1. Tourists' sample profile

Due to their close proximity to and easy accessibility from the large urban metropolis of Athens, the Cyclades tend to attract a very high share of domestic tourism (Prokopiou et al, 2018; Sarantakou & Tsartas, 2015). The majority of our respondents were domestic tourists—and repeat visitors -while the second most important visitor group were international tourists arriving from the EU, followed by international tourists arriving from outside the EU. Of the three islands, it is Santorini that seemed to attract the majority of international tourists outside the EU. All respondents declared interest in visiting all types of local cultural attractions, events, and sites, especially restaurants, food festivals/ gastronomy events, and 'traditional'/ folklore-related sites/ activities. However, the most important factors that seemed to influence their decision to make these visits tended to be practical ones, mainly recommendation by their hotel, price, and physical accessibility, and least of all personal interest, recommendation by

other people or inclusion in a tour package. These facts underline the overarching basic visitation motive for the Cyclades, which is not, at least consciously, cultural, even though Cyclades tourists spend a considerable part of their holiday time engaging in/with cultural attractions/ events/ site visits.

Table 2. Businesses' sample profile

Both culture- and tourism-related enterprises were included in the business survey. Since the latter took place during August and September, we experienced certain difficulties. Since August is the highest tourism peak month in Greece, business owners or managers were often too busy or reluctant to complete the questionnaire. Especially for the islands of Andros and Syros, the tourist season ended abruptly in early September due to the pandemic and, therefore, businesses could not be easily reached as they closed down for the fall much earlier than usual. The interviewed businesses showed a very positive attitude towards cultural tourism (acknowledged its significance and high potential in the area) and stressed the need for governmental support, both in terms of general cultural tourism development and vis-à-vis relevant local/ regional entrepreneurship.

4.1 Changes in tourist ways of traveling due to the COVID-19 pandemic

4.1.1 Covid-19 and ways of traveling at the time of the pandemic

Figure 2. Ways of traveling at the time of the pandemic

Regarding the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the respondents' ways of traveling (closed-ended question), during the tourism season of summer 2020, 27% of our case study participants replied 'Very much', followed by those who answered 'Much' (27%), while 25% of the interviewed tourists chose to remain neutral. This finding points to the very significant impact of the pandemic on local cultural tourism, out of fear of the risks entailed in traveling,

corresponding state restrictions on traveling, tourists' low propensity to travel, and their actual limited traveling activity.

4.1.2 Changes in traveling patterns as a result of the pandemic

The majority of tourist respondents stated that the Covid-19 pandemic imposed serious restrictions on their frequency of traveling, especially on traveling abroad (open-ended question). In specific, the majority stated that they took shorter holidays than usual. Several European tourists stated that they chose Greece because they felt safe there and trusted the way that the Greek State had handled the pandemic and its repercussions in the country.

Furthermore, based on our tourist sample profile, it becomes evident that many domestic tourists chose 'staycations' in the Greek islands, rather than travel abroad. Those who did manage to travel in 2020 expressed their concerns about the safety measures that they had to take vis-à-vis the pandemic, referring to feelings of being 'cautious' or 'anxious' while traveling. They also described feelings of insecurity and annoyance for having to wear masks and constantly use sanitizers. Many also stated that they tried to avoid public transport as much as they could, preferring to rent their own vehicles of transportation when traveling around the islands.

In contrast, about 20% of our tourist respondents declared that the pandemic did not change the way that they travelled around the islands at all. The only activities that were missed, according to their responses, were attending local fiestas, festivals, and arts events (banned for fear of overcrowding), activities that have traditionally been very much tied into summer holidays in the Cyclades.

4.1.5 Impact of the pandemic on the businesses

Figure 3: Impact of the pandemic on the businesses

For the majority of interviewed businesses, the impact of the pandemic and the ensuing lockdown was considerable, as evidenced in the responses of our business survey participants (closed-ended question). In specific, 76% of them replied that their businesses were strongly impacted in terms of 'reduced international visitor numbers', 71% replied that they were strongly impacted in terms of 'Reduced levels of bookings', 66% replied that they were strongly impacted in terms of 'Cancellations of bookings' and 59% replied that they were strongly impacted concerning 'Rearrangements/ postponements of bookings', while more than half of these businesses were forced to close. The answers thus obtained corresponded with and affirmed officially quoted impacts of the pandemic on Greek tourism, both at the national and at the local/ regional levels.

4.1.6 Businesses' measures to offset the negative impact of the pandemic

The measures followed by our respondents to combat the negative impacts of the pandemic (closed-ended question) specifically were: Development of new initiatives and products (24%); Development of new digital services (39%); Enhancement of existing digital services (42%); Exploration of new markets (45%); Maintenance of connections with existing customers (50%); and Advertising as normal (48%). However, based on the fact that these percentages are all below 50%, we may deduce that these business owners/ managers seemed rather disinclined to take any forward-looking actions, but rather assumed a 'let's-wait-and-see' attitude as to how the situation would evolve.

4.1.7 Businesses' measure(s) regarding employees

The grave measures that businesses were reportedly forced to take because of the pandemic (closed-ended question) were as follows: first to lay off staff (98%), then to furlough staff with pay (93%) or partial pay (82%), while 88% of them redirected their staff to other tasks. New hiring was evidently severely affected. It should be noted that furloughed staff in Greece during

the Covid-19 pandemic was paid a horizontal 534 Euros/ month. For some employees, this could often be considered as partial payment, in comparison to their monthly salary (i.e. 1,000 Euros/ month). For employees who received minimum salary in Greece (e.g., 683 euros/month), the answer could be furlough with pay.

4.1.8 Government assistance received by the businesses to offset pandemic impacts

The Greek state seems to have responded to the pandemic crisis in the business world, mainly through incidental financial assistance. More specifically, 56% of our respondents replied to this closed-ended question that their businesses received financial assistance in the form of furloughs and 23% replied that they received financial assistance in the form of loans, while only 16% mentioned 'General advice'. These findings are also in agreement with corresponding relevant national and local statistics.

4.1.9 Sustenance of business

In consequence to the trends presented above, only a small number of the business representatives who participated in our survey (27%) replied (closed-ended question) that they had managed to sustain their business for one full year, followed by 25% of respondents who replied 'six months', and 17% who replied 'nine months'; only 7% were reportedly able to sustain their business for over a year. Based on the researchers' personal observation and according to the opinions of most local/ regional tourism stakeholders, business owners seemed to have used funds from the previous profitable fiscal years (2018 and 2019) towards their 2020 business needs and survival.

4.2 Changes in cultural tourists' satisfaction in the Cyclades, due to the Covid-19 pandemic

4.2.3 Difference in tourist satisfaction with Cyclades cultural tourism experience before and during the Covid-19 pandemic

Figure 4. Difference in tourist satisfaction with Cyclades cultural tourism experience before and during the Covid-19 pandemic

Finally, when asked (closed-ended question) to compare their current visit experience with that/ those of pre-pandemic times, the highest percentage of our respondents (39%) stated that they were more satisfied with their visit to the area on the occasions that they visited it before the pandemic. The main reasons are related to travel restrictions during the time of the pandemic, or the lack of cultural activities and events due to pandemic risks and their repercussions. Interestingly, 17% percent of respondents said that they could not see any difference between the two points in time, which must be viewed in the general context of high levels of tourist satisfaction from cultural tourism in the Cyclades, as a rule (Trip Advisor, 2022). On the other hand, a surprising 18% stated that their tourism experience was better during the summer of 2020 than other visits in the past. It can be inferred from the researchers' overall knowledge and personal observation that the latter interviewees were the type of tourists who tend to prefer quieter holidays to those who prefer the hustle and bustle of busy towns, crowded beaches, party/feast atmosphere or noisy situations. Moreover, those tourists who completed our survey questionnaires offline had the opportunity to share with the researchers their enthusiasm for enjoying a very relaxing and unusually crowd-free August in the three island destinations. This was especially the case with the island of Santorini, which has been experiencing conditions verging on 'overtourism', during the summer months of the previous several years (Constantoglou & Klothaki, 2020, Sarantakou & Terkenli, 2019).

5. Contextualizing survey findings with stakeholders' views and visions: a discussion

This section brings together and discusses the mutually-reinforcing survey findings with the output obtained from the two supplementary methods employed in this study, namely the in-depth stakeholder interviews and the round-table discussion among agents of cultural tourism

in the Cyclades. Again, this discussion is organized on the basis of the article's three research questions.

The cultural tourism sector's transformation as brought about by the pandemic was revealed by findings pertaining mainly to the first and second research questions—namely showing the impact of the pandemic and consequent governmental measures on the Cycladic tourism industry. Concerning the first research question (impact on tourists), our tourist survey results overwhelmingly point to a serious curtailing of tourist mobilities, in terms of type of tourism, ratio of domestic vs. foreign tourism, frequency of travel, length of stay at the destination, type of transport used, preferred type of destination, behavioural patterns during traveling, and cultural activities engaged in at destination. This is a significant trend, even though the Greek islands and Greece, more generally, were broadly (nationally and internationally) considered to be comparatively safe tourism destinations during the pandemic year (2020), due to successful measures taken by the Greek government to address hygienic risks and create a relatively safe environment for tourism and travel in the country (Constantoglou & Klothaki, 2021; National Geographic, 2020). Moreover, the very high percentage of repeat-travellers to the Cyclades, even in times of the pandemic, indicates a degree of customer loyalty to the destination, which forebodes continuing tourism-related opportunities for these islands in the post-pandemic era.

Moving on to the sector of culture, according to one of our round-table discussants, 'culture suffered the greatest impact of the pandemic', while another explained:

'all parts of the cultural sector have been gravely affected, as regards all aspects of these sectors, so much so that people in the sector did not believe that it would be possible for them to return to their professions and creative activities/occupations, after all these crises are over. But also we, as spectators, are held back by both the pandemic and the concomitant State measures (both psychologically and institutionally) in enjoying culture as we did before.'

A great number of cultural activities ingrained in local ways of life were banned or did not take place during 2020, especially those which attract a large number of participants/spectators, such as religious feasts and cultural festivals. On the other hand, Cyclades tourists tended to indulge in more expenses and/ or spend more money at the destination, during the summer of 2020 (Kathimerini 28/11/2021, participant observation); as pointed out by one of our interviewees, ‘they sought to invest in the crisis.’

Concerning the second research question (impact on businesses), the businesses' perspectives as regards the impacts of the pandemic and ensuing governmental measures were very grave, both as regards culture/ tourism employment and business economic sustenance and survival. They tried to resolve it through a reconsideration of the ways in which their services and practices could be improved, promoted, and digitalized, but they generally seemed to be in a rather ‘frozen state’- neither very active nor particularly optimistic or positive as regards such measures. Since the Covid-19 pandemic presented an unprecedented situation, business owners/ managers seemed rather disinclined to take any forward-looking actions, but rather assumed a ‘let’s-wait-and-see’ attitude as to how the situation would evolve. This attitude was reinforced by the overall feeling that they were left to their own devices by the State; this feeling was amplified by the fact that Cycladic (cultural) tourism businesses viewed governmental measures as lacking and insufficient or misguided. On the other hand, the Vice Mayor of Santorini responsible for cultural affairs on the island pointed out that the respite from rampant tourism growth and activity on Santorini that the pandemic brought about allowed for a period of recollection and re-evaluation of shortcomings in the sectors of culture and cultural tourism, towards more sustainable future solutions, as well as to the turn towards these sectors’ digitalization.

Round-table discussants especially noted the absence of the State in culture and tourism planning/ development/ regulation/ legislation/ management (including cultural tourism). They

referred to the State's misguided actions in combatting the pandemic and repercussions towards the sustainable continuation of island life and culture, leading to an even more pronounced and grave loss of cultural traditions/ heritage, jobs, and opportunities for further overall—as well as specifically cultural—development. Conclusively, there was a general round-table agreement that all sides/ parties/ sectors/ levels of governance ought to be involved in the islands' cultural tourism development, a need and demand that also became very evident to the researchers, through on-site participant observation.

Finally, as regards the third research question (the outcome and reactions both of the tourist and the local sides), although the Covid-19 pandemic brought about significantly adverse impacts on tourism (im)mobilities and traveling patterns, variably addressed by local actors and factors, tourist satisfaction with their visitation practices in our case study was reportedly mixed. Certainly, the 'overtourism' phenomena, which presented a degree of inconvenience to the tourist experience prior to the pandemic (i.e. traffic problems in Syros and Santorini), abated during the summer of 2020. The questionnaire survey findings indicate that the Cyclades tourists themselves tended to be somewhat more satisfied on all counts with cultural tourism as they reportedly experienced it before the onset of the pandemic. They tended to rate such overall experiences in the past more favourably than those at the time of the survey. However, a significant percentage of them, especially when answers 'experience is better now', 'no difference' and 'I cannot say' are taken together into consideration, no clear preference emerges for tourism as it used to be overtourism after the onset of the pandemic. This clearly signals the strong and sustained popularity of (cultural) tourism in the Cyclades. It further illustrates the capacity of Cycladic tourism to cater to the needs and demands of a (mostly loyal and growing) clientele seeking a combination of natural and cultural assets that cater significantly to remote or exclusive, but also to quieter, small-scale tourism mobilities and experiences.

Looking ahead, according to the Cyclades Chamber of Commerce representative, what was deemed most imperative was that culture is embraced by the local side as part of its everyday practice and reality rather than becoming a tourism product. The Commerce representative especially rallied for the preservation or reinstatement and further evolution/development of ‘the islands’ culture, which is a tangible fact of everyday life, but also attracts tourists... You either make it your reality or you lose it—and you need to show this, in action (both to ourselves and to our guests).’ As an example, he brought up the rich, but perishing, architectural heritage and the shipyards/ ship-making tradition of Syros, which have historically been of utmost importance for the economy of Syros and a crucial part of the island’s traditional life.

Future visions and goals, as described by the Ephor of Antiquities for the Cyclades (belonging to the Archaeological Society of the Ministry of Culture), point to:

‘a different type of tourism that does not destroy the landscape (either built or not) and the tourism product itself, but rather protects and promotes the intangible heritage of the islands, ways of life and activities in rural areas and in the sea: these are clearly deteriorating and in the process of being irrevocably lost. To prevent that, we need to propagate this other type of tourism (cultural tourism is part of it), in order not to turn islands into ‘tourism paradises’ or simply stop mass tourism from inundating them (that is undesirable).

All of our interviewees and stakeholders expressed the need to coordinate and regulate such inflows better, in order to realize such alternative types of tourism, acknowledging the importance of culture for tourism, and cultural tourism itself as ‘the future of the islands’.

Finally, our stakeholders viewed the pandemic as an opportunity to address these impediments to future tourism growth and development. They stated that emphasis on ‘green’, sustainable and milder forms of tourism had been already evolving in the Cyclades even before the pandemic and postulated that these developments will become more and more important in

the future. Another realization was ‘not a lack of visions vis-à-vis culture, but a lack of planning and mechanisms to materialize these visions and produce tangible results towards their future sustainable development’ (National Tourism Organization of Greece representative). This stakeholder went on to argue that pandemic-induced developments may lead to forms of cultural tourism that are more spatially secluded and engage smaller numbers of people/participants, to more abstract types of experiences, more authentic experiences, or more controlled and hybrid big-event activities, simultaneously digitalized: ‘these developments will also favour those parts of the society with moving disabilities and other particularities, who were formerly unable to attend to/participate in these activities/ events.’

6. Conclusions

The onset of the pandemic has certainly ushered a change in mind sets as regards tourism, in Greece, as elsewhere: different ways of looking at existing issues, situations, issues, or problems and a turn away from ‘mass’ tourism towards more sustainable future forms of mobilities (INSETE 2021: 46; Jacobsen et al., 2021; Knezevic et al., 2021). As overtourism was not an issue for the Cyclades, with the exception for Santorini (i.e. depletion of water resources, and infrastructural deficiencies), this issue was rarely addressed by the study participants. During the summer of 2020, the pandemic principally shifted local priorities in Cyclades (cultural) tourism towards more realistic goals of survival.

On the one hand, our findings concerning the first research question show that cultural tourists adapted to the new reality by generally curtailing traveling patterns in terms of choice of location (mostly domestic), length of holidays (shorter), and type of activities sought (more dispersed, outdoor activities). However, if the demand side suffered, the supply side of Cyclades cultural tourism suffered even more, with businesses struggling to survive the crisis, on all fronts. Thus, according to our second research question findings, Greek tourism

entrepreneurs expressed fatigue in having to assume the brunt of sustenance of the country's tourism sector without the State's help, called to operate in a 'hostile environment' (Terkenli & Georgoula, 2021). Although significant progress had been initiated and instigated in the years before the Greek socio-economic crisis (2008-2015) and the Covid-19 pandemic, in terms of more sustainable/ 'green', innovative/ creative, and technologically upgraded cultural development and cultural tourism development, this progress was put to hold by the pandemic, with unpredictable future prospects. The outcome of this crisis (third research question findings), then, was revealed to be grave, in terms of both cultural tourists' relative dissatisfaction and of the local supply-side left to its own devices to struggle for solutions. Nevertheless, a certain optimism was shown to prevail among the study participants from all sides involved, based on new emerging opportunities, commitments, interests, delineating a growing forward-looking dynamism.

This exploratory study laid out the main trends and characteristics of ongoing change in cultural tourism in the Cyclades—a heavily tourism-dependent destination—caused by the pandemic and concomitant government measures, from the perspectives of tourists and local stakeholders/ leading actors in the fields of culture and tourism. The Cyclades become an interesting case study, in this regard, also due to their resource fragility and insular vulnerabilities. The latter characteristics put this island archipelago at a precarious position as regards its cultural tourism development, which ought to have a mild and not a mass character, while future tourism expansion ought to aim towards counterbalancing tourism seasonality. The study's findings indicate that such a prospect may clearly be materialized through cultural tourism development, on the basis of cooperation among civil societies and relevant individuals and entrepreneurs, on the one side, and the State, on the other. According to one of our stakeholders, this goal may not be as lofty as it sounds because 'even just nature and the general

environment/ landscape of the Cyclades are so unique and special, that they elicit/ inspire such higher goals and visions for their future.’

This research was undertaken in the context and at the crossroads of still-evolving extreme uncertainties and volatile conditions created by the onset of the pandemic and concomitant governmental measures. It certainly suffers from limitations owing to its exploratory scale and scope, and calls for much more developed, nuanced, targeted, and in-depth quantitative and qualitative data collection, through multi-methodological approaches, placing this research in its specific, comprehensive social, economic, cultural context and prospects of sustainable local/ regional development. However, the insights drawn from this study will be useful in short-, medium-, and long-term future cultural tourism planning, marketing, and management in similar small-island tourism-dependent destinations. Such insights (i.e., vulnerabilities and deficiencies, visions, and assets, etc.) may open up new post-crisis horizons that are soundly based on destination needs and priorities. For instance, this study’s findings most significantly expose long-underlying structural problems to the island’s tourism sector, which have thus become clearer and more specific.

The pandemic brought new parameters to bear on cultural tourism in the Cyclades. These parameters certainly pave the way for the rejuvenation of cultural tourism after the end of the pandemic, but with several collateral losses, i.e., a severe rise of unemployment in related sectors, while many people employed in the sector of culture have already changed profession. All pertinent changes ought to be taken into consideration in any cultural tourism analysis and future plans, prospects, and interventions concerning the islands’ highly tourism-dependent economies. Such caution, contextualized in terms of the multi-dimensional new realities dawning for (cultural) tourism in the post-Covid-19 era, applies to similar small-scale and size, tourism-dependent economies, with similar development characteristics and structural inefficiencies. However, such future applications and extrapolations require much further,

broader, ongoing, and in-depth research undertakings, in order to build more robust and generalizable conclusions.

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Figures and tables

Figure 1. The case study of Cyclades: Andros, Santorini, and Syros Islands.

Source: Cartography and Geoinformatics Laboratory, Department of Geography, University of the Aegean.

Table 1. Tourists’ sample profile

Features	Characteristics of the tourists’ profile sample			
	Gender	males	females	
37%		63%		
Age	20-30	30-50	50-60	over 60
	19%	66%	4%	11%
Country of origin	Greece	Europe	USA	
	84%	15%	1%	

Educational level	Secondary education	High School graduates	Vocational education	University/Master/ PhD graduates
	1%	12%	15%	72%
Profession	Professional	Clerical support/ Elementary worker	Manager	Other
	29%	36%	21%	14%
Household income	Less than €10,000	€11,000 - €20,000	€20,000 - €40,000	More than €40,000
	19%	35%	21%	25%
Household composition	Single person	Couple	Three or four persons	More than 5 persons
	46%	28%	24%	2%

Table 2. Businesses' sample profile

Features	Characteristics of the business profile sample			
Type of business	Accommodation	Visitor Attraction	Restaurants	Other
	48%	27%	9%	16%
Average number of visitors per year	<1.000	1.000-5.000	5.000-10.000	10.000-50.000
	53%	29%	12%	6%
Total visitor capacity	<1.000	1.000-5.000	5.000-10.000	10.000-50.000
	58%	13%	9%	20%

Type of Accommodation	4* & 5* Hotels	2* & 3* Hotels	1* Hotels/guesthouse	Airbnb type of Vacation rentals
	20%	24%	40%	16%
Number of beds in accommodation	<10	11-20	21-50	51-100
	28%	50%	16%	6%
Estimated occupancy	2-4 nights	5 - 7 nights	8 nights	
	70%	30%	0%	
Business ownership	Family business	Private business	International chain	Public sector/cooperation
	55%	39%	3%	3%
Years of establishment	>10 years	5-10 years	3-5 years	Last 3 years
	60%	19%	8%	13%
Busiest times of business	Summer	Spring	Autumn	School holidays/Christmas
	99%	52%	36%	11%
Origins of visitors	Tourists-European Union	International tourists-outside the EU	Domestic tourists	
	28%	12%	40%	

Figure 2. Ways of traveling at the time of the pandemic

Figure 3: Impact of the pandemic on the businesses

Figure 4. Difference in tourist satisfaction with Cyclades cultural tourism experience before and during the COVID-19 pandemic

